

Bringing Your Homeland with You: First Generation Migrants from the Balkans' Decision to Pass on Their Language to Their Descendants (Austria)

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Study hosted on <https://kinguistics.wordpress.com/>.

Abstract. Migrations have always been a part of history, especially for people from the Balkan Peninsula. Due to economical, political, or military events, people from the Ex-Yugoslavian republics reached out to many western European countries, hoping they will help them find a peaceful home in the future. One of these countries is certainly Austria – only in 1991, over 198.000 people from former Yugoslavian countries fled to Austria (Bonifazi, Mamolo, 2004) , mainly to its capital – Vienna. These people, most of them without ever encountering with German, made various decisions when it came to passing the essential part of their heritage to their descendants – their mother tongue. Some did not encourage their children in keeping the language alive, resulting in them being semilingual. What the main goal of this study is, is to find out what attitude towards passing on their mother tongue to their children is, and what results did it bring. Through a questionnaire, fifty people between the ages of 28 – 68 decided to share their point of view. The study shows that the majority of people find it really important for their children to understand and speak Bosnian/Serbian/Croatian – almost 90%, although only a bit more than 40% speak only Bosnian/Serbian/Croatian to their children. This also results in the fact that only 35% of children speak only their mother tongue with their parents, and over 20% of children speak only German to one another.

Keywords: Balkans; Austria; migration; language; integration

1 Introduction

People from former Republics of Yugoslavia have migrated a lot – you can find their minorities in Germany, France, Russia, USA, Argentina, Australia... One particular city holds a large community of Yugoslavian people – Vienna. In 2020, 5.3% of Vienna's population was from Serbia; 2.1% from Bosnia; and 1.5% from Croatia. Of course, you have to take into the consideration people with Austrian citizenship whose country of origin is still one of the former Yugoslavian Republics. So let's back up a bit — there are several reasons why these people moved — the first wave in 60s and 70s was labour induced. Later, in the 90s, people sought a home while fleeing from a war. In the 2000s, the bad economic situation made people reach for Vienna once again. A lot of them started their families in Vienna and raised their children differently.

My study wanted to know — what are their reasons to pass or not to pass their mother tongue (in future will be called — BCS (stands for Bosnian, Croatian, Serbian) to their children. 55 people were questioned, and their average age is — men 44, women 45. Their mother tongue is BCS, and they all immigrated as adults.

2 Study

This first graph (Figure 1) shows you their approach to German before moving to Austria. As you can see, women paid more attention and their answers are more detailed, while men answered with sufficient or no knowledge at all. Women show that their interest in language and culture before moving was higher, indicating that they were more interested in fitting in and finding their place in a new environment than men. When taking a look at their current knowledge, we can see that while men are mostly good and really good, 20% of women are still not fully comfortable with German. This may be due to the fact that after the migration wave in the 90s, during the Yugoslavian war, men were the ones working, while most women stayed at home with children.

Figure 1: Participant's knowledge of German before moving to Austria (men & women).

Figure 2: Participant's knowledge of German now (men & women).

When taking a look at the language of a partner and its connection to the parent's decision to pass on BCS to their children, people whose partners grew up with German really wanted their children to learn BCS,

while the ones who's partners grew up speaking both German and another Slavic languages found it relatively important. 94% of people whose partners grew up speaking BCS as well succeeded in passing on BCS to their children as well, but some of them didn't find it as important as one might assume.

Figure 3: Language importance.

Now let's take a look at the relationship between the language a parent spoke to its child and in what language does the child speak to the parents now. Great majority speaks only BCS to their kids — 44%, but 62% of children speak more German than BCS to their parents, although BCS was mostly the only language spoken by their parents at home. 1% of parents spoke only German, and so did their kids, but according to data, no kids favoured when it wasn't spoken by parents at all.

Figure 4: Languages spoken with children.

A bit more than 4% of parents were favouring German when talking to their children, and this got me thinking — why? Well, when looking at the data, the main reasons these people left were war induced. We can then look at this from a perspective of a post war trauma — by deciding to favour German and speak less or no BCS with their children, people are actively trying to cut all their ties to the past.

I also took a look at how much are the parents bothered when their children make mistakes in BCS. Of course, the ones who speak German with each other (not with parents) tend to make more mistakes and their parents tend to correct them more often – 40% of children whose parents correct their mistakes very

often speak only German with each other, while 50% of children whose parents corrected them rarely speak mainly BCS with each other. Only 2% of people said that passing on BCS to their children is not important. Again, those are the people who were forced to leave due to the war, so yes.

Column %	No, never	sometimes	regularly	Very often	Very rare	NET
English	0%	8%	0%	20%	0%	5%
BCS & German, but German <u>more often</u>	0%	38%	20%	40%	25%	27%
BCS & German, but BCS <u>more often</u>	33%	0%	0%	0%	50% ▲	11%
<u>Both BCS & German, no preferences</u>	0%	23%	27%	0%	0%	16%
German	33%	23%	13%	40%	13%	20%
BCS	33%	8%	33%	0%	13%	18%
NET	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

45. Which language(s) do your kids speak with each other? by 48. Do you ever correct your kids while speaking BCS?
 sample size = 44; total sample size = 56; 12 missing; 95% confidence level

Figure 5: Languages spoken between children.

When comparing the level of education and the existence of nostalgia, I found that the more people are educated, the less nostalgic they feel – probably because they moved because of a good job opportunity and are aware of the current situation in their home country. People with only high school tend to be more nostalgic, but they also favour German in their everyday life, indicating that they want to fit into the community. When looking at Figure 2, the level of education compared to the language participants spoke to their children, we confirm the theory that high school educated people have a desire to fit in – 100% of them who only spoke German to their kids are only high school educated, and 50% of the ones who prefer German over BCS. When taking a look at college/university educated participants, none of them exclude BCS from the communication, although we can see that a large amount of them choose German over BCS in everyday conversation. A lot of educated people hold a great amount of grievance and anger that, although they spent years getting educated in their home country, they still had to leave and find a better place to live. Some of them also found partners whose mother tongue isn't BCS, so that could be the reasons for preferring German, although a high amount also speaks only BCS to their children as well.

This next fact was really surprising! Although TV channels in BCS were still watched at home after moving to Austria, the majority of children from those households speak German with each other. This may be due to the fact that no German knowledge was shown by the parents, therefore, children used it as a secret language in order to talk between each other. Again, if we take a look at the number of people who would love to, but don't watch TV in BCS, their children also prefer German, which indicates that the lack of media support can be sensed in children's language preference.

Column %	yes	no	NET
College/University	38% ▼	73% ▲	46%
Elementary school	10%	0%	8%
High school	38%	18%	34%
Higher education	13%	9%	12%
NET	100%	100%	100%

What level of education do you have? By Do you feel nostalgic about your homecountry?

Column %	BCS & German, but German more	BCS & German, but BCS more	Both BCS & German, no preference	German	BCS	NET
College/University	50%	43%	20%	0%	50%	43%
Elementary school	0%	7%	0%	0%	15%	9%
High school	50%	43%	40%	100%	20% ▼	36%
Higher education	0%	7%	40%	0%	15%	13%
NET	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Figure 6: Levels of education compared to language(s) spoken.

Column %	yes	no	I would love to, but I don't	NET
English	3%	20%	0%	5%
BCS & German, but German more	30%	0%	50%	27%
BCS & German, but BCS more	14%	0%	0%	11%
Both BCS & German, no preference	16%	20%	0%	16%
German	22%	0%	50%	20%
BCS	16%	40%	0%	18%
NET	100%	100%	100%	100%

45. Which language(s) do your children speak with each other? by
58. Do you ever watch TV in BCS sample size = 44; total sample size = 56; 12 missing; 95% confidence level

Figure 7: Language preference and TV programmes.

This last table shows how religion is connected to the children's interest in BCS language and culture. It affects it for certain, but it is not a key. You can see that no children whose parents are going to church or mosque are not entirely interested in the culture, while the ones that don't do rarely, have children who are not very fond of their heritage. It is also to be seen that 44% of children whose parents never go to church speak only German with each other. Then again, when looking at the column no. 8, which stands for really interested, 67% of these children's parents don't go to church. So, as I said, it can make a change but it doesn't mean it will entirely affect the child's interest.

Column %	0	1	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		NET
yes	0%	0%	0%	0%	20%	67%	75% ▲	0%	25%	42%		30%
never	50%	0%	0%	50%	40%	0%	25%	67%	50%	25%		35%
sometimes	50%	100%	100%	50%	40%	33%	0%	33%	25%	33%		35%
NET	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%		100%

18. Do you ever go to church/mosque in Austria? by 73. How high is your children's interest in BCS culture and language?
sample size = 40; total sample size = 56; 16 missing; 95% confidence level

Figure 8: Percentage of children who attend church and their interest in it.

3 Conclusion

My conclusion is that, although people moved due to so many different reasons and most of them weren't pretty, the majority of them still brought a little piece of their home with them and are willing to pass it on. The trauma induced by the war can be a factor that makes people want to forget their language, but these people are in a minority. When looking at data about their children's BCS knowledge, I am not surprised to find that, even they are interested in the culture and language, some of them still identify themselves with German more than with BCS, especially when it comes to talking to their siblings.

4 References

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